

Mercury Acetamide as a Mercurating Agent. Part II. Mercuration of Phenols.

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Since mercury acetamide has been found to be an effective reagent in the mercuration of cyanoacetamides (Naik and Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 29), it was proposed to extend its use in the mercuration of some phenols and examine how far it resembled mercuric acetate in its mercurating action. With this end in view, the interaction of mercury acetamide with *o*-nitrophenol, *p*-nitrophenol, α -naphthol, β -naphthol, and phloroglucinol was studied.

In all cases monohydroxymercuri derivatives were obtained, except in the case of phloroglucinol, which gave a trihydroxymercuri derivative. The reaction in the case of *o*-nitrophenol may be represented as follows:

Similarly *p*-nitrophenol, β -naphthol, α -naphthol and phloroglucinol gave 2-hydroxymercuri-4-nitrophenol (II), 1-hydroxymercuri- β -naphthol (III), 4-hydroxymercuri- α -naphthol (IV), and 2:4:6-trihydroxymercuri-phloroglucinol (V) respectively. The constitutions assigned to the compounds follow from their reactions with bromine, whereby the HgOH group is substituted by Br.

Compounds (I), (II), (III), and (IV) dissolve in dilute sodium hydroxide solution giving hydroxymercuri sodium-phenolates. Compound (V) is insoluble in sodium hydroxide. Dilute hydrochloric acid has no

action on compounds (I) and (II), but concentrated hydrochloric acid decomposes them giving mercuric chloride and the original phenols. Compounds (III) and (IV) are easily decomposed by dilute hydrochloric acid while compound (V) dissolves undecomposed in concentrated hydrochloric acid and can be reprecipitated on dilution.

Compounds (I), (II) and (V) are not affected by hydrogen sulphide, while compounds (III) and (IV) first form a yellow product, which decomposes slowly into mercuric sulphide. Similarly (I) and (II) are not attacked by potassium iodide, whereas (III) is completely decomposed giving a quantitative yield of potassium hydroxide.

1-Hydroxymercuri- β -naphthol, when dissolved in just the necessary amount of sodium hydroxide and shaken with carbon disulphide, gave β -naphthol-1-mercuri-mercaptan:

Such a course of reaction is not at all uncommon, since similar compounds have been obtained by Koten and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 2754) from aryl and alkyl mercuric hydroxides in presence of traces of alkali on shaking with carbon disulphide. When compounds (I) and (II) were similarly treated, a very small amount of a product separated, which was insufficient for analysis. *o*- and *p*-Hydroxymercuriphenols, prepared by the method of Whitmore and Middleton (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 622), when similarly treated, gave bulky precipitates of phenol-*o*- and *p*-mercuric mercaptans respectively.

Sodium thiosulphate is a reagent most generally used for converting the organo-mercury compounds of the type $R \cdot HgX$ to the compounds R_2Hg (Pesci, *Gazzetta*, 1899, *i*, **29**, 394; Dimroth, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 2855; Kharasch and Piccard, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1861, *et seq.*). 2-Acetoxymercuri-4-nitrophenol, when treated with this reagent, gave 2:2'-mercuri-bis-4-nitrophenol.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Hydroxymercuri-2-nitrophenol (I).—A hot solution of mercury acetamide (3.2 g.) in dilute alcohol (1:1) was added to *o*-nitrophenol

(1.4 g.) dissolved in the same solvent and the mixture heated for 4 hours on a water-bath, when a granular orange coloured product separated. This was filtered and washed with water, alcohol and ether. It is practically insoluble in all organic solvents, but is soluble in dilute sodium hydroxide and acetic acid. The pure product turns dark above 248° but does not melt till 285°. (Found: Hg, 55.92; N, 4.14. $C_6H_5O_4NHg$ requires Hg, 56.34; N, 3.94 per cent).

Action of bromine.—About 1 g. of the above compound was suspended in water and bromine dissolved in a solution of potassium bromide was added. When the colour of bromine was no more absorbed, it was warmed gently on a sand-bath. On cooling crystals appeared, which were filtered and washed with water. It was crystallised twice from dilute alcohol. The pale yellow needles melt at 88°. It is identical with 4-bromo-2-nitrophenol obtained by Dahmer (*Annalen*, 1904, 333, 353).

Action of hydrochloric acid, potassium iodide, hydrogen sulphide and ammonium sulphide.—4-Hydroxymercuri-2-nitrophenol, when heated with dilute hydrochloric acid, remained unchanged. When it was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid it went into solution, which on cooling gave crystals. After recrystallisation, it was identified as *o*-nitrophenol, m. p. 45°.

When boiled with a solution of potassium iodide in water 4-hydroxymercuri-2-nitrophenol remained unchanged. No change was noticed when hydrogen sulphide and ammonium sulphide were added to the aqueous suspension of the above compound.

2-Hydroxymercuri-4-nitrophenol (II) was prepared by mixing equimolecular proportions of mercury acetamide and *p*-nitrophenol, dissolved in a hot aqueous alcoholic solution and keeping for 24 hours. The yellow product, which separated, was filtered and washed with distilled water, alcohol and ether. It darkens above 248° but does not melt till 285°. (Found: Hg, 56.16; N, 4.09. $C_6H_5O_4NHg$ requires Hg, 56.34; N, 3.94 per cent). When treated with bromine as in the preceding case, it gave a compound, m. p. 113-14°, which was identified as 2-bromo-4-nitrophenol, prepared by Diels and Bunzl (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 1491).

2-Acetoxymercuri-4-nitrophenol was obtained by adding 25 c. c. of glacial acetic acid to 2 g. of compound (II) and heating for 10 minutes. It turns dark above 240° but does not melt till 285°. (Found: Hg, 50.01. $C_8H_7O_5NHg$ requires Hg, 50.38 per cent).

2 : 2'-*Mercuri-bis-4-nitrophenol*. — 2-Acetoxymercuri-4-nitrophenol (2g.) was added to a solution of sodium thiosulphate (1.3 g.) in water. The compound went into solution which deposited a sulphur yellow product after 5 days. It turns dark brown above 190° but does not melt till 235°. (Found: Hg, 41.70. $C_{12}H_8O_6N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 42.02 per cent).

1-*Hydroxymercuri-β-naphthol* (III) was obtained similarly from equimolecular quantities of β-naphthol and mercury acetamide dissolved in a mixture of alcohol and water (2:1), m. p. 210° (decomp). (Found: Hg, 55.48. $C_{10}H_8O_2Hg$ requires Hg, 55.55 per cent). When heated with dilute hydrochloric acid it gave β-naphthol (m. p. 122°) and when treated with bromine as in the preceding case it gave 1-bromo-β-naphthol, m. p. 84° (Smith *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1879, 35. 789). When suspended in water and treated with hydrogen sulphide for 12 hours it gave black mercuric sulphide.

0.1804 G. of the above compound was added to a solution of potassium iodide (2 g.) in water and boiled for 1 hour. The alkali liberated was equivalent to 14.6 c. c. of 0.0686 *N*-hydrochloric acid, showing that 1.99 equivalents of alkali were liberated and that the splitting of C-Hg linkage was quantitative.

1-*Acetoxymercuri-β-naphthol* was prepared by dissolving it in hot acetic acid solution. It melted at 185°. (Found: Hg, 49.64. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3Hg$ requires Hg, 49.75 per cent).

Action of carbon disulphide on compound (III).—A solution of 2 g. of this compound in just the necessary amount of dilute sodium hydroxide when shaken with 2 c. c. of carbon disulphide, gave a yellow product, which blackens above 145° but does not melt till 285°. (Found: Hg, 52.71; S, 8.35. $C_{10}H_8OSHg$ requires Hg, 53.19; S, 8.51 per cent).

4-*Hydroxymercuri-α-naphthol* (IV) was prepared in the usual way from mercury acetamide and α-naphthol. It darkens gradually above 240° but does not melt till 285°. (Found: Hg, 55.11. $C_{10}H_8O_2Hg$ requires Hg, 55.55 per cent). On treatment with bromine in a solution of potassium bromide in water it gave a product, m. p. 128° identified as 4-bromo-α-naphthol prepared by Reverdin and Kauffman (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 3054).

Trihydroxymercuriphloroglucinol (V) was obtained on mixing phloroglucinol (1 mol.) and mercury acetamide (3 mols.) dissolved in hot water. It turns brown at 185° and then gradually blackens but does not melt till 285°. (Found: Hg, 76.99. $C_6H_6O_6Hg_3$ requires Hg,

77.52 per cent): On treatment with bromine as in the preceding cases tribromophloroglucinol, m. p. 153°, (Zincke and Kegek, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1732) was obtained.

Phenol-o-mercurimercaptan.—A solution of *o*-chloromercuriphenol (2 g) in just the necessary amount of sodium hydroxide, was shaken with 2 c. c. of carbon disulphide, when the mercaptan separated out as a yellow compound. It blackens above 130° but does not melt till 285°, (Found: Hg, 60.85; S, 9.59. C_6H_6OSHg requires Hg, 61.34; S, 9.81 per cent).

Phenol-p-mercurimercaptan was prepared in the same way as above from *p*-chloromercuriphenol. It blackens above 150°. (Found: S, 9.51. C_6H_6OSHg requires S, 9.81 per cent).

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